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Project-induced individualized acquisition of competences in a Bachelor's degree course

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this pilot-module was to test how individualized learning can be structured when based on a precise, pre-defined task. Each individual task was part of a group task, solving a specific problem from the industry. Each student defined within such industry project a subtask and the individual learning outcomes respectively. These learning outcomes did not only serve to complete the subordinate group task, but aimed at the acquisition of defined competences. Experts supported the students in the process of defining their individual learning outcomes. This ensured quality and

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quantity of the learning outcomes. Additionally, the students were supported by coaches to reflect their learning process and learning strategies.

The pilot module is designed in such a way that it closely reflects learning in a professional context: completing a common task based on the contribution of individual subtasks is the foundation for individual learning processes. Thus, the pilot module is similar to the concept of Team Academy, but on a much smaller scale (3 ECTS module).

In the evaluation of the module, the learning coaches noticed that managing the group task and managing the individual learning project in a self-directed way is rather complex for a single 3 ECTS module. Especially the forming phase of the groups took too much time and prevented students to start their individual learning projects in a timely manner.

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a pilot module carried out within the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences & Arts Bachelor study program Business Engineering / Innovation. The primary objective of developing this 3 ECTS elective was to evaluate the feasibility of deriving highly individualized learning projects from a practical problem from industry which has to be solved by a group of students.

The learning processes of students in educational (tertiary-level) institutions differ significantly from those in which adults engage in professional (work-place) settings. In a professional setting learning is generally motivated by and closely associated with a concrete assignment, and the learner's compilation of content from various subject areas as he/she tackles this assignment resembles the work of an artist creating a mosaic. The pilot module creates a learning situation which corresponds more closely to the needs and approaches of the working professional

The basic concept of the pilot module is shown in Fig. 1: A group of students is taking care of a practical problem from industry. The industrial project is acquired by students, the formation of the groups is self-organized. The group breaks the project aims down into subtasks which can be handled by individual group members. Based on these subtasks, each student then develops his / her learning objectives in two steps: 1) Writing a success story: After completion of the learning project, in which professional situations will the student be able to demonstrate his / her newly acquired competencies? 2) Detailing the success story: which competencies are needed in order to master the situation described in the success story?

The responsibilities for both the industrial project and the individual learning projects lie in the hands of the students. According to their needs, they have the possibility to get advice either from content experts, who are experts in the subject area of the individual learning projects, or from learning coaches, who are experts in learning processes and methodologies.

Fig. 1. Concept of the pilot module

This paper first presents the theoretical background of the pilot module, followed by a description of the underlying methodology. Findings of the module evaluation are then presented. The final sections reflect on and discuss the methodological approach as well as potential improvements and the further development of the module.

1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE MODULE CONCEPT

The engineer’s prospective professional environment is growing ever more complex due to the fast pace of technological change and, especially, digitalization. Consequently, engineers must acquire new strategies to develop their competencies [1]. Traditional tertiary institutions no longer live up to these challenges [2]. They must not only impart knowledge but also competences required for autonomous learning and self-organization.

For some years now, educators have been turning from traditional motivational psychology towards theories which focus on the attainment of goals. Early on, motivational theorists such as Deci and Ryan [3] shifted their interest from the effects of external influences on motivation to the subject’s self-direction. According to their well-known Self-Determination Theory, motivation is derived from three universal, innate psychological needs: competence, autonomy and social integration. Subjects are more motivated to take action a) if they believe their behavior will afford them

greater competence (self-efficacy), b) the more freedom they have in initiating and implementing a certain behavior (autonomy) and c) the more social interaction or connectedness the behavior fosters (gain in interpersonal relatedness).

A concept for a teaching module with highly individualized learning goals has been described in [4]. In this pilot study the focus was on maximizing each student's individual degree of freedom in designing their own learning project. Each student was moreover responsible for acquiring the self-defined target competencies. According to his / her needs, the student could get support from learning coaches and from content experts. This module satisfies each of the psychological needs identified by Deci and Ryan [3]: The module relies not only on the initiative of participants but in particular on their efficacy; greater autonomy is the core concept of the module; and social interaction and connectedness developed among the module participants, who have several extensive group meetings.

The individual learning projects were not linked by a common group assignment.

One acquires the ability to organize oneself primarily through exercising self-organization. Relevant academic literature refers to educational settings designed to foster self-organizational competence as »self-directed learning« [5] or, often synonymously, as »self-organized learning« (»SOL«).

There is no standard definition for SOL or self-directed learning. “Nonetheless, the approaches have a common denominator: Their focus is on the learner, who initiates and organizes his own learning processes. Objectives such as the promotion of self-determination, self-directed activity and responsibility for one's own learning process are to be found in many approaches.” [5]

Examples of SOL applied to a specific, common task or mission. Especially worth mentioning are the Action Learning [6] and Team Academy [7] theories.

The pilot module that is described in this paper was designed to combine highly individualized learning goals with an underlying common group project. The learning goals are individually derived from the project and may cover much more than what is needed to solve the project task. Therefore the concept is similar to Action Learning and to Team Academy, though framed in a 3 ECTS project module. O'Neil, Yorks and Marsick [8] have categorized the different approaches in Action Learning in a four-level Action Learning Pyramid. This pilot module is located on level three, stepping up from level one (problem solving and implementation of solutions) and level two (problem re-framing, learning a process for learning from work experience) by adding personal learning goals, emphasis on reflection and learning styles.

2 TEACHING METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology underlying the design and implementation of the pilot module.

2.1 Selection of team projects and student participants

Preliminary to the module start all students were invited to submit ideas for the group projects. These group projects had to fulfill the requirements of being relevant for a specific company and being manageable by a team of 3-5 students within the

predefined time frame (workload 90 hours per student). After pre-selection of appropriate projects by the lecturers in charge, the student initiators of the group projects pitched their ideas to all other interested students. Subsequently the students were asked to organize themselves in project teams of appropriate size and to divide the project into individual subtasks, for each of which one student assumed responsibility. A total of 15 students within different semesters participated in this pilot module.

2.2 Establishment of individual learning objectives

The first assignment for each project group was to define the overall project goal. Additionally each participant had to write a personal success story based on the chosen individual subtasks. Such a success story was to describe the specific situation which they wished to be able to master after completing the module, i.e. which competences the student wished to acquire during the course of the module. Subsequently, the students contemplated which competences they already had and which they would need to acquire in order to accomplish their success story. To enable students to formulate individual learning objectives, a ‘competence pyramid’ based on Bloom’s cognitive taxonomy was introduced [9]. The success story together with the competence pyramid also served as the basis for the final module exam. The following figures show examples of a success story and competence pyramid.

After this module I will be able to explain the advantages of Scrum to the CEO of a company in order to simplify the management of complex projects. I will be able to explain how difficulties in a project can be identified in a timely manner. I can describe limitations and assessment criteria for Scrum.

Fig. 2. Sample success story

Fig. 3. Sample competence pyramid (in green: existing competences, in yellow: targeted competences)

2.3 The learning process and evaluation of learning progress

Each student was assigned a content expert possessing expertise in the content area chosen. These content experts were responsible for a) assessing the individual success stories and learning objectives with respect to whether the learning objectives were sufficiently challenging but also manageable within the scope of the module and b) assessment of their students' achievement in the final module examination. In addition, the students were given the option of coaching sessions with the content expert for expert advice and with the learning coaches to reflect on their learning process and, if appropriate, adjust their course of action. In a mid-term steering meeting the students of each project team presented the current status of their attainment of learning objectives as well as the level of progress of the overall group project and received individual feedback.

2.4 Assessment

Assessment was threefold, consisting of a group presentation in which the overall project achievements were to be highlighted, as well as assessment of each individual's acquired professional expertise on the one hand and acquired learning competencies on the other. The aim of the group presentation was to show to which degree the project objective had been fulfilled and how the individual sub tasks had contributed to this goal. For the individual examination each student was asked to demonstrate the newly acquired competences. The students themselves contemplated and decided in advance what they wanted to present in order to prove their mastery of the content. They simulated a situation which corresponded to their success story. In the final part of the individual examination the student's content expert and the learning coach asked clarification questions to the content and learning process. The success story and the competence pyramid served as benchmarks for the assessment of the student's newly acquired expertise.

3 MODULE EVALUATION

The pilot module was evaluated using three methods: students' evaluation, feedback of content experts and reflection of learning coaches/module responsible. The latter is integrated in the discussion chapter.

3.1. Students' evaluation

The students were asked in the beginning (week 1), middle (week 8) and end of the module (week 14) to quantitatively answer the following two questions, using the online questionnaire tool Qualtrics®.

Question 1: To which degree do/did the following persons/aspects contribute to your individual learning project (Assign a percentage!)? Assessment of each of the following was requested: team, common project aim, learning coaches, content experts, internet, and other persons not participating in the module.

Question 2: Please assess: To which degree are you contributing/have you contributed to your individual learning project in comparison to the above-mentioned persons/aspects (Assign a percentage!)?

The results were analyzed statistically with IBM® SPSS® version 25. Due to the small sample size (n=16), a non-parametric statistical analysis with a level of significance of 5% was employed.

As Figure 4 shows, the analysis of question 1 revealed that the internet as well as the common task were the main aspects contributing to the individual learning project. Furthermore, the group was felt to contribute less and less to the individual learning project over time. The statistical analysis shows, however, no change in comparative significance for any contributing factor over the course of the module.

Fig. 4. Results of question 1 – contribution to individual learning project

The analysis of the answers to question 2, as depicted in figure 5, shows that the students quantified their own contribution to the individual learning project at the beginning of the module as approximately 60%, whereas they attributed to all other persons/aspects combined approximately 40%. In the middle of the module, these values increased to 72% (own contribution) and decreased to 28% (other persons/aspects). In the second half of the module the attributions changed slightly to 67% and 33% respectively. The differences from week 1 to week 8 are statistically significant, the differences from week 8 to week 14 are statistically not significant.

Fig. 5. Results of question 2 – degree of individual versus other persons'/aspects' contribution

In addition to the quantitative analysis described above, the students were asked in open questions after completion of the module to give feedback regarding motivation, support provided in the module for their learning process, professional relevance and level/amount of learning. Selection of individual learning goals and achieving these goals with self-determined time management were factors which students mentioned as motivating. On the other hand, using the competence pyramid as a tool for understanding current and envisioned competence levels as well as organizational issues within the teams were mentioned as demotivating factors. Relevance to the professional world was an aspect which supported the learning process, whereas various students would have wished to have closer contact to the content experts or even regular checks of their individual learning progress for a better support of the learning process. Students were satisfied with the amount of their learning and understood the professional relevance of such module. Some students suggested that the module should be extended to a 6 ECTS module due to the comparatively high level of complexity of this specific learning setup.

The specific feedbacks mentioned above are not representative for the whole group, but were chosen rather to convey an impression of what was received well and what might want further improvement. All students recommended continuing to offer such a module and affirmed its vocational relevance.

3.2. Feedback of the content experts

The content experts were asked to give feedback concerning this concept of individualized learning. This feedback can be summarized in the following findings:

- It is not clear if students' motivation is higher than in traditional modules. There seems to be a high motivation at the beginning of the learning project, which decreases in the course of the project.
- Employing Bloom's pyramid to facilitate the description of learning objectives is an effective method. However, for students and for the content experts to be

able to apply it, a clear introduction, some training and a common understanding are necessary.

- The students are challenged not only with their main learning goals, but in this setting also with several aspects of project management. These aspects of project management should be accounted for by adding them to the individual learning pyramid.
- The setting up and start of the learning project is the most crucial part and needs quite intense and thorough support by the content expert. The quality and intensity of the relationship between expert and student can vary considerably during the course of the module, depending on the student's needs and skills. Individualization of coaching (timing, intensity, duration, objectives) is necessary in such a setting.

4 DISCUSSION

As opposed to traditional course modules, the lecturers in this pilot module hand over to the students the full responsibility for determining the thematic orientation of their work, defining their learning objectives and organizing their learning process. The students are part of a group that solves a practical problem from industry. This group task is the source for the learning projects of the individual students.

The main conclusion of the assessment of this pilot module is that the combination of a group task with individual learning projects seem to exceed the scope of a 3 ECTS module. Several feedbacks from students, the qualitative feedback from the content experts and the impression of the learning experts/module responsible support this conclusion. Forming the group and organizing the group task took too much time and left the individual students in substantial uncertainty concerning their learning goals. This might have led to the content experts' perception that in some cases motivation decreased in the course of the project. Furthermore, quantitative findings reveal that students' assessment of their own contribution to their learning project compared to the contribution of other persons increases in the first weeks of the project, i.e. students overestimated the contribution of other persons at the beginning of the learning project.

Nevertheless, many aspects of the pilot module were evaluated positively by the students, content and learning experts, including:

- Individualization gives students the possibility to strengthen individual competence profiles.
- Self-organization of learning projects allows highly individualized time management.
- The setup of the module examination allows the students to prove their newly acquired competences on the one hand. On the other hand, students reflect on their learning process and can hereby identify success factors for their own individual learning strategy.

For the Bachelor's program in Business Engineering, this pilot module has proven the feasibility of individualized modules. To reduce the complexity experienced in this pilot module, a future implementation in the curriculum will focus on the individual learning

projects omitting an underlying common group project. This simplified module structure has been validated and described in [4].

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